

THE ALKALOIDS OF *RAUWOLFIA CANESCENS*, LINN. PART I

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An alkaloid Rauwoscine ($C_{21}H_{28}O_3N_2$, m.p. $231-32^\circ$) has been isolated from *Rauwolfia canescens*. Its physical and chemical properties have been studied and a number of salts and derivatives prepared. The colour reactions of rauwoscine show it to be quite different from other *Rauwolfia* alkaloids but similar to yohimbine. Rauwoscinic acid has been obtained from the alkaloid presumably by the hydrolysis of a CO_2Me group in rauwoscine; the acid has been reconverted into the alkaloid.

Although *Rauwolfia serpentina*, Benth. (N.O. *Apocynaceae*) has been the subject of a number of investigations (Siddiqui and Siddiqui, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 667; 1932, 9, 539; 1935, 12, 37; 1939, 16, 421; Van Itallie and Steenhauer, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1932, 270, 313), other species of *Rauwolfia* do not appear to have received much attention. Greshoff (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3537) reported the presence of an alkaloid (0.4%) in the bark of *Rauwolfia canescens*, but he did not purify his base or determine its molecular formula and properties. Recently Koepfli (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2412) reported the isolation of a crystalline alkaloid, rauwolfire, $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$, m.p. $235-38^\circ$ (decomp), from an African species, namely *R. caffra*.

The present communication deals with the isolation and examination of an alkaloid from *R. canescens*, known locally as "Barachéndá." It is a small shrub inhabiting the moist and hot regions of India. Its roots are sometimes used to adulterate those of *R. serpentina*. The alkaloid appears to be different from any of the *Rauwolfia* alkaloids, so far described, and has consequently been named *Rauwoscine*.

Rauwoscine is distributed throughout the plant. Root-bark contains 0.1%, stem-bark 0.2% and leaves 0.5% of pure rauwoscine, besides other bases, an account of which will be given in a subsequent communication.

Rauwoscine forms thick, pale yellow plates, m.p. $231-32^\circ$ (decomp.)* having $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -40^\circ$ (alcohol). The analytical data of the base, as also of a number of salts derived therefrom, indicate the formula $C_{21}H_{28}O_3N_2$ which is further supported by the M.W. data. It is devoid of *N*-methyl and methylenedioxy groups, but the presence of one methoxy group has been established. The base does not give any colouration with ferric chloride.

* The melting points recorded in this paper, are uncorrected.

It is faintly alkaline to litmus and possesses a very bitter taste, which is also shared by its salts. The salts of the monacidic base are generally well-crystalline. The hydrochloride and nitrate are neutral, while the sulphate and oxalate show an acid reaction towards litmus. The picrate is orange, while the chloroplatinate is amorphous and pale orange in colour.

Rauwolscine gives characteristic colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid and other alkaloidal reagents, as shown below.

TABLE I.

Reagent.	Colour.
H ₂ SO ₄ (conc.)	Blue with a violet tinge changing to red.
Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ +K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	Deep blue changing to green
Fröhde's reagent	Navy blue, then purple and finally yellow.
Erdmann's reagent	Bluish green, gradually changing to yellow.
Mandelin's reagent	Blue, changing to yellow.

Precipitates are formed from the hydrochloride with many reagents, such as phosphomolybdic acid (greenish white), iodine in potassium iodide (reddish yellow, 1 in 1000 dilution), potassium mercuri-iodide (white), potassium bismuth iodide (orange-red). Of these the last named compound can produce a precipitate in a dilution of 1 in 200,000.

The analytical data as also the colour reactions are, therefore, different from those of the other Rauwolfia alkaloids. Rauwolscine, however, shows a considerable amount of similarity in properties and colour reactions with yohimbine. This is illustrated in the following table.

TABLE II.

Comparison between yohimbine and rauwolscine.

Reagent.	Yohimbine.	Rauwolscine.
Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Blue with a violet tinge	Same
Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ +K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	Deep blue with violet tinge changing to green.	Same
Conc. HNO ₃	Yellow.	Same
Fröhde's reagent	Navy blue, then yellow.	Same
Erdmann's reagent	Greenish blue, then green, finally yellow.	Same
Mandelin's reagent	Deep blue, then reddish yellow.	Same
Specific rotation		
Free base	+56° (alcohol)	-40° (alcohol)
Hydrochloride	+105° (water)	+74° (water)
Melting point		
Free base	234° (decomp.)	231-32° (decomp.)
Hydrochloride	295-300° (decomp.)	278-80° (decomp.)
Crystalline form and colour	Colourless needles.	Pale yellow thick plates.

Rauwolscine oxalate.

Rauwolscine oxalate.

Rauwolscine.

Rauwolscine nitrate

Rauwolscine hydrochloride.

Melting point depression was observed when the two bases as also their hydrochlorides were mixed together showing that they are different. The physical properties of the base, rauwolscine are also different from

other alkaloids of the yohimbine group having the same molecular composition.

Although rauwolscine is precipitated from an aqueous solution of its salts by means of ammonia, prolonged contact with concentrated ammonia or aqueous potassium hydroxide converts rauwolscine into a water-soluble compound, m.p. 262-64° (decomp.). This substance is neutral to litmus, but is more soluble in dilute sodium bicarbonate solution than in the same volume of water. It is also soluble in moderately strong ammonium hydroxide. The ferric test is negative. Apparently the transformation product contains a CO₂H group and has consequently been named rauwolscinic acid, which shows absence of methoxy group by Zeisel's method. The assumption is, therefore, made that rauwolscinic acid is formed from rauwolscine by the hydrolysis of a CO₂Me group. Rauwolscinic acid could be reconverted into rauwolscine by the action of methyl alcohol and hydrogen chloride. These observations prove the presence of a CO₂Me group, which has so far not been detected in other Rauwolfia alkaloids, but which is present in yohimbine and some other alkaloids.

It is presumed, therefore, that although rauwolscine and yohimbine are not identical, the main features of the structures of the two alkaloids may be very similar.

The pharmacological action of rauwolscine, as also further work on the constitution of the alkaloid, is in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Isolation of Rauwolscine.—*Rauwolfia canescens* were collected from the District of Howrah (Bengal) and were identified by Prof. A. Das-Gupta of Bangabasi College, Calcutta, to whom the author offers her best thanks. 2 Kg. of air-dried leaves were percolated thrice with rectified spirit (50 litres) containing 0.1% acetic acid at room temperature. The combined bright green extracts were concentrated to about 800 c.c. on the water-bath under reduced pressure. The dark green viscous liquid was poured into cold water (600 c.c.) in a thin stream with constant stirring and allowed to stand. Resinous matters which had separated out were then filtered off and the aqueous filtrate was thrice shaken up with ether (200 c.c. each time) to remove oily and other impurities. The red aqueous solution was then covered with ether (300 c.c.), made just basic by the addition of concentrated ammonia, and the liberated base taken up in ether. The aqueous solution was shaken up three times with ether (300 c.c. each time) till a test portion on removal

of ether and acidification with hydrochloric acid failed to give any appreciable amount of precipitate with potassium bismuth iodide. The aqueous solution showed the presence of not inconsiderable amount of alkaloids as tested by Dragendorff's reagent. Efforts are being made to isolate the water-soluble alkaloids.

The combined ethereal extracts were washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate and concentrated to about 250 c.c. A solution of anhydrous oxalic acid in ether was then gradually added to the above extract till no further precipitation was observed. The crude oxalate of rauwolscine, thus obtained, was collected, washed with ether, and then heated with absolute alcohol on the water-bath for three hours to dissolve gummy substances and colouring matters, cooled, filtered and washed with absolute alcohol; yield 13 g. Further purified by two or three crystallisations from hot water, rauwolscine oxalate formed clusters of silky radiating colourless needles, m.p. 245-46° (decomp.). It is acidic to litmus and liberates iodine from a mixture of aqueous potassium iodide and potassium iodate. Rauwolscine oxalate has two molecules of water of crystallisation which are completely removed on drying *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 125-30°. (Found in dry specimens: N, 6.27; OMe, 7.1. $C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2 \cdot H_2C_2O_4$ requires N, 6.3; OMe, 6.98 per cent).

To prepare the free base, the oxalate (3 g.) was dissolved in warm water (400 c.c.), cooled and made just alkaline with ammonia. The cream-coloured needles were collected, washed with water and dried in a desiccator over calcium chloride. Two or three crystallisations from benzene gave pure rauwolscine, m.p. 231-32° (decomp.), not raised by further crystallisations; yield 2 g. It has $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -40^\circ$ (0.266 g. of substance in alcohol, $l=50$ mm.). No significant loss in weight occurred on drying *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 120-25°. (Found: C, 71.5; H, 7.5; N, 8.1; OMe, 8.52 per cent). Another specimen crystallised from alcohol and dried at 140-45° *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 2 hours was also analysed [Found: C, 71.2; H, 7.6; OMe, 8.5. M.W. (titration), 355.8, 355. $C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2$ requires C, 71.2; H, 7.3; N, 7.91; OMe, 8.76 per cent. M.W., 354).

Rauwolscine is freely soluble in ether, ethyl acetate, chloroform, and hot alcohol, less soluble in benzene, and very sparingly soluble in petroleum ether and water.

Rauwolscine hydrochloride was obtained by dissolving the base in the minimum quantity of hot 2*N*-acid. The colourless prismatic needles of the *hydrochloride* obtained on cooling the solution were recrystallised from hot water, m.p. 278-80° (decomp.). It has $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +74^\circ$ (0.2750 g. of substance in 25 c.c. of water, $l=50$ mm.). The salt is neutral to

litmus and suffered no loss in weight on drying at 140° for 2 hours in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 . (Found : Cl, 9.09. $C_{21}H_{28}O_3N_2.HCl$ requires Cl, 9.09 per cent.)

Rauwolscine nitrate, obtained in a similar manner, is also neutral to litmus, but is less soluble in water than the hydrochloride, m.p. $257-58^{\circ}$ (decomp.). The salt also appears to be free from water of crystallisation. (Found in specimen dried at $130-35^{\circ}$ for 2 hours in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : N, 9.85. $C_{21}H_{28}O_3N_2.HNO_3$ requires N, 10.0 per cent).

Rauwolscine Sulphate.—The precipitated base was dissolved in a slight excess of 2*N*-sulphuric acid and the solution almost evaporated to dryness. The cooled residue was washed with cold absolute alcohol and crystallised from the same solvent, when colourless needles, m.p. $256-57^{\circ}$ (decomp.), were obtained. It is more soluble in water than the hydrochloride and unlike the hydrochloride showed acidic reaction towards litmus. (Found in specimen crystallised from water and dried at $110-15^{\circ}$ for 2 hours in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : S, 7.02. $C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2.H_2SO_4$ requires S, 7.08 per cent).

Rauwolscine Chloroplatinate.—An amorphous orange-yellow precipitate was obtained on adding an excess of 5% chloroplatinic acid to a concentrated solution of the hydrochloride in water. It was washed with hot water and dried at $115-20^{\circ}$ for 3 hours in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 . m.p. $255-57^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found : Pt, 16.72. $C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2.H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 17.53 per cent). Attempts to crystallise the compound from a large volume of alcohol resulted in the formation of the hydrochloride and other amorphous products. Rauwolscine chloroplatinate is insoluble in acetone.

Rauwolscine picrate was obtained as an orange precipitate on treating an ethereal solution of the base with ethereal picric acid. Crystallised from alcohol it formed shining orange plates, m.p. 208° (decomp.). [Found in specimens dried for 2 hours at 110° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 54.6 ; H, 6.7 ; N, 10.2, 10.3. $C_{21}H_{28}O_3N_2.C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH.2C_2H_5OH$ requires C, 55.1 ; H, 6.1 ; N, 10.37 per cent).

Rauwolscinic Acid.—Finely divided rauwolscine (0.1 g.) was covered with ammonia (30 c.c., *d* 0.88) and allowed to stand at room temperature in a closed vessel. The base passed into complete solution in course of a week. The clear pale yellow solution was evaporated on the water-bath to a small volume, acidified with *N*/2-acetic acid and then completely evaporated to dryness. The brown residue was washed with a small quantity of cold water and crystallised thrice from hot water, when pale brown prisms, m.p. $262-64^{\circ}$ (decomp.) were obtained. The product was neutral to litmus but dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and dilute acids in the cold. It has a slightly bitter taste. Rauwolscinic acid has one

molecule of water of crystallisation which is lost on drying in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 4 hours at $120-25^\circ$. (Found in a dry specimen: N, 8.23. $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.23 per cent). A methoxy estimation proved the absence of methoxy groups. This acid is being further investigated.

Rauwolscine from Rauwolscinic Acid.—A stream of dry hydrogen chloride was passed through rauwolscinic acid (0.1 g.), suspended in methyl alcohol (5 c.c.), till saturated. The acid passed into solution and the clear solution on standing overnight deposited colourless, shining needles of rauwolscine hydrochloride. These were collected and washed with cold methyl alcohol, m.p. $276-78^\circ$ (decomp.).

To prepare the free base, the hydrochloride was dissolved in warm water (20 c.c.), the solution cooled and made just alkaline with dilute ammonia. The cream-coloured needles which separated out, were collected, washed with water, crystallised from dilute alcohol and finally from benzene. Pale yellow plates (0.09 g.), m.p. $230-31^\circ$ (decomp.), were obtained. The product did not depress the m.p. of rauwolscine, when mixed together.

Photomicrographs of rauwolscine and some of its salts are reproduced on p. 35.

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